

“A study to assess English Communication Skills among Student Nurses of Selected School of Nursing, New Delhi”

*Ms. Sarita Upadhyaya¹, Ms. Rohini Sharma²

¹Nursing Tutor, Apollo School of Nursing, Indraprastha Apollo Hospital, Delhi-76

²Vice Principal, Apollo School of Nursing, Indraprastha Apollo Hospital, Delhi-76

*Corresponding author: **Ms. Sarita Upadhyaya**

Nursing Tutor, Apollo School of Nursing, Indraprastha Apollo Hospital, Delhi-76

Abstract

Introduction: Communication is an important aspect of behavior; human communication is affected by all factors that influence human behavior. Effective communication helps to prevent problems from occurring and plays a role in conflict resolution. The aim of this study was to assess the effectiveness of communications skills in General Nursing & Midwifery (G.N.M) Students. Objectives: The objectives of this study are to assess the English Communication Skills among Nursing student, to find out the association between English Communication Skill and selected demographic variable and to suggest School authority on improving English Communication of the students as per the result. Method: The study was conducted using Quantitative approach with descriptive research design on 131 sample, G.N.M Nursing Students of Apollo School of Nursing, New Delhi, by using purposive sampling techniques. A Structured Knowledge Questionnaire on “Communication Skills” was used for collecting data. Data analysis was done by descriptive & inferential statistics. Result: The result reveal that, 79(60.3%) student nurses had average communication skills, 51(38.9%) were had poor communication skill and 1(0.7%) had good communication skill. Conclusion: The study concluded that, most of the student nurses had average skill on English communication and factors responsible to have poor & average communication are, lack of knowledge about grammar, inadequate vocabulary, not able to speak fluently and incorrect pronunciation.

Keywords: English communication, language skill, student nurses.

INTRODUCTION

Good communication is the bridge between confusion and clarity.” - Nat Turner

Communication refers to transferring messages between a sender and a receiver¹. The word “communication” originates from the Latin word *communicare* that means “to make something common or general”. The term “communication” means: to say, to inform, to be in connection with, to connect, to transfer, so a communicative person would be one that is capable of easy conduct with other people, that is talkative and easy to approach². Communication has various roles. It may designate the transfer of information, problem solving, decision making and satisfying needs¹.

Communication is an important aspect of behaviour; human communication is affected by all factors that influence human behaviour³. Communication may be intentional or unintentional, may involve conventional or unconventional signals, may take linguistic or non-linguistic forms, and may occur through spoken or other modes. Communication skills are important in building interpersonal relationships with friends, peers, and colleagues in a work environment. Having effective communication skills allows a person to build trust and rapport with the people they surround themselves with. Being an attentive listener that makes decisions based on the feelings of others is a person that is well-received in friend groups and the workplace. Effective communication helps prevent problems from occurring and plays a role in conflict resolution. Remaining calm during arguments allows a person to explain their intentions in a cognitively aware way instead of letting high emotions take over.

English as a language never enjoyed this position from the beginning. World history in and after 14th century has a major role to play in making this language powerful and useful. In today's date it is not only a major language all over the world but also the official language in many parts of the world. Many people depend on this language for their mere survival and sustenance. Many may be surprised to know that English as language was never used for official purposes even in England up to 11th and 12th century. In England people used to use rich languages like Latin, French and Spanish. The dominance of each and every language over the history has been dictated by the might the countries enjoyed. As England was ruled by the France and other nations for a long period of time, they never had the opportunity to develop their own language. Till late 13th century the script of English language was not completely developed. The first writing in English which can be claimed as a piece of literature dates back to late 13th century.

Communication is a dynamic interactive process that involves the effective transmission of facts, ideas, thoughts, feelings, and values. It is not passive and does not just happen; we actively and consciously engage in communication in order to develop the information and understanding required for effective group functioning. It is dynamic because it involves a variety of forces and activities interacting over a period of time. The relationships of people engaged in communication continuously grow and develop. Communication can also be understood as an exchange of meaning and understanding. Thus Effective communications can have a positive impact on the patient-provider dynamic in numerous ways. It can allow patients to be better educated about their own health, which could enable them to embrace proactive health and wellness strategies. It can also help patients develop a comprehensive understanding of current care strategies involving their health, including acute health situations. The increased presence of technology makes effective communication even more important in health care and can help mitigate the potential impact of health misinformation that could otherwise lead patients to make poor or improper decisions about their health. It can also help improve communication among other health care professionals who may need to coordinate care across multiple facilities, which lead to improved opportunities for delivering care. English Communication is one of the essential foundations of human existence, yet most people overlook the need to enhance their communication skills. An effective communication skill is a must whether it is individual or a group. English communication skill is the art and technique for communicating and persuading. Thus, a communication skill is the ability to use language and express information. A communication skill is the set of skills that enables a person to convey information so that it is received and understood. Therefore, communication skills are necessary and important for G.N.M. students.

This study assumes that, nursing student will have some existing knowledge on English communication, and the knowledge regarding English communication will be assessed by structured knowledge questionnaire. The objectives of the study are, to assess the English Communication Skills among Nursing student, to find out the association between English Communication Skill and selected demographic variable and to suggest School authority on improving English Communication of the students as per the result.

METHODOLOGY

Materials and Methods: A quantitative research approach with descriptive research design was used to conduct research study at selected School of Nursing of Delhi. The data was collected in the month of March and analyzed as per the objectives of the study in May 2024, to assess communication skill of the student nurses with certain demographic variables like age, qualification, current year of study, family income, family types, medium of language instruction in previous school. Total of 131 samples (student nurses) was taken by using nonprobability purposive sampling technique. The samples were given open and close ended structured questionnaires. Before the interview, written consent was taken, aims and objectives were explained to them.

Tools: The Structured Questionnaire were used to assess the communication skill of the student nurses comprised of demographic variables like age, qualification, current year of study, family income, family types, medium of language instruction in previous school, and open-ended structural questionnaire consisting of 4 aspects of communication (Reading, Writing, Listening and Speaking).

Result: The study result based on the data collection from 131 participants.

Table No. 1. Socio Demographic Variables N = 131

S.NO	DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (F)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1.	AGE (IN YEARS)		
	Below 20 years	46	35.1%
	20 – 25 years	82	62.5%

	More than 25 years	3	2.2%
2.	QUALIFICATON		
	10 +2	117	89.3%
	ANM	6	4.58%
	NON NSG. COURSE	8	6.10%
3.	CURRENT YEAR OF STUDY		
	First Year	49	37.40%
	Second Year	49	37.40%
	Third Year	33	25.19%
4.	TYPE OF FAMILY		
	NUCLEAR	87	66.4%
	JOINT	44	33.5%
5.	FAMILY ANNUAL INCOME		
	≤50,000	82	62.5%
	50,001-1,00,000	35	26.7%
	> 1,00,000	14	10.6%
6.	SCHOOLING		
	PRIVATE	84	64.1%
	GOVT.	47	35.9%
7	MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION IN PREVIOUS SCHOOL		
	ENGLISH	101	77.0%
	HINDI	19	14.5%
	REGIONAL	11	8.3%

Data represented in the above table showed that, most of the students 82 (62.5%), of the GNM nursing students were in the age group of 22-25 years, and 46 (35.1%) were below 20 years and 3 (2.2%) were above 25 years. Majority 117 (89.3%) of the GNM nursing students were have done 10+2, Hindu, 8 (6.10%) were done non nursing course and 6 (4.58%) were done ANM. Majority 87(66.4) of them belongs to nuclear family and 44(33.5) of them are in joint family. Majority of the GNM nursing students 82(62.5%) have their annual family income 50 thousand & less, 35(26.7) were having annual family income 50,001-1,00,000 and 14 (10.6%) were having more than 1 Lakh family income. Most of the 84 (64.1%) GNM nursing students have completed their schooling from private school and 47(35.8%) of them completed their schooling from government school. Majority of GNM students 101(77%) were had English language of instruction in their previous school, 19(14.5) were had Hindi language as an instruction and 11(8.3%) were had their instruction in their regional language.

Table No.:2 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Communication Score of Student Nurses (N=131)

Communication Skill	Criteria		Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
	Score	%		
Poor Skill	0-40	Below 45%	51	38.93
Average Skill	41-70	46%-78%	79	60.30
Good Skill	71-90	Above 79%	01	0.76

Table No. 2 reveal that, 79(60.30%) student nurses had average communication skills, 51(38.93%) were had poor communication skill and 1(0.76%) had good communication skill.

Table No.: 3 Effectiveness of The Structured Communication Skill N-131

Test	Mean	Median	S.d	Chi-square	D.f	Value (tab)
Overall Mean, Median and Standard Deviation	42.92	44	11.24	2.65	2	1.39

Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table No. 3 shows the mean (42.92), median (44) and standard deviation (11.24). The result obtained after statistical analysis shows that the obtained' chi square value is 2.65. In the Table 3 chi square value for degree of freedom 2 at 0.05 level of significance is 1.39 so, there is no any association between demographic variable and English communication skill.

Table No.: 4 score of Communication Skill of Student Nurses as Per Their Academic Year (N= 131)

COMMUNICATION SCORE	1 ST YEAR	2 ND YEAR	3 RD YEAR
POOR	43	8	0
AVERAGE	6	41	32
GOOD	0	0	1

Table No. 4 shows, communication skill score of student nurses as per their present year of study. Majority of 1st year having poor English communication. However, most of the 2nd year and 3rd year had average English communication skills that is 41 & 32 respectively and only 1 participant had good English communication skill among all three batches.

DISCUSSION

The present study was aimed to assess the effectiveness of Communication skills among G.N.M Nursing Students of Apollo school of Nursing. The research group found in Assessment of G.N.M Students had 79(860.30%) average knowledge 01(0.76%) had good knowledge and 51(38.93%) had poor knowledge.

The findings of the present study were supported by the study conducted by Dr. Abdul Malik Abbasi. The study explores the English language spoken issues at university level. The paper further found some phonetic and cognitive aspects as problematic i.e., pronunciation, grammar, listening, and reading skills. This study is supported by the study conducted by Mellati Mandasari The result of the research in generally, 91% students had problems in oral communication class. Specifically, from the data analysis, the students had problems in linguistic factors.

On the basis of the findings of the study recommendations are offered for further research that, the study can be replicated on the large sample so that findings could be generalized and Similar study can be conducted on B. SC, M.Sc. and other than nursing course.

CONCLUSION

This study was aimed to describe the students' problems in English communication. Overall, it can be concluded that, most of the student nurses faced problems in linguistic factors such as lack of knowledge about grammar, inadequate vocabulary, not able to speak fluently and incorrect pronunciation. From the discussion above the researcher found that the student's problem in English Language such as accuracy, pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar, and fluency. Beside that the students still used their local accent include their pronunciation.

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